

EXPLANATION OF THE EXPRESSION OF THE QUALITATIVE AND RELATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF AN OBJECT, PHENOMENON, PROCESS IN A NON-PHILOLOGICAL GROUP

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the development of a nationally oriented methodology for teaching the Russian language to the Uzbek audience. Taking into account the peculiarities of the native language of students when teaching the Russian language is one of the most important factors in its assimilation. It touches upon the difficulties of phonetic and grammatical nature, typical for Uzbek-speaking students, and offers recommendations for overcoming them. The article contains practical material.

The main condition for the effective development of the speech ability of students is the solution of the problems of speech activity in the lexical and grammatical study of parts of speech, taking into account the phased passage from one level to another, more complex one.

The implementation of the principles of developmental education, which form the basis of the methodology for developing the speech ability of students when studying the name of an adjective, contributes to the improvement of students not only language, but also speech ability, and also ensures the formation of self-awareness, self-esteem, self-importance of each student's personality.

Language, as a unique system created by the people throughout the history of its development, performs various functions associated with a particular area of human

activity. Among them, the leading function is communication. That is why the problem of the formation of communicative skills, the education of students of the gift of a living word, the culture of monologue and dialogic speech in the Russian language lessons is currently becoming extremely relevant. A survey of rural schools in the Republic, an analysis of the oral and written speech of students "and adults" show that they do not adequately possess such qualities of good speech as accuracy, clarity, richness, expressiveness, purity and euphony, and in this regard, the student is faced with a number of problems, already coming to the university. In the conditions of bilingualism, the issues of the struggle for the purity of Russian speech deserve special attention. One of the most common speech diseases is the use of foreign words and phrases without the need. Mixed speech is not always pleasing to the ear. It

testifies to the low verbal culture of a speaker of two languages. This indicates a lack of desire to enrich the vocabulary and variety of synonymous means for adequate expression of one's thoughts and feelings.

These aspects of the development of students' speech skills should be confirmed in the methods of teaching the Russian language, where primary attention is paid to the study of grammar, as well as the formation of students' communicative competence. It is gratifying to note that there is a program aimed at establishing an organic connection between the study of Russian grammar and the development of students' speech abilities. Great opportunities for this lie in the names of adjectives - in the source of the most numerous army of words after nouns. At the lessons of the Russian language, along with adjectives, forms of other parts of speech (in particular, nouns) that function in speech as signs of an object and actions should be considered. In terms of its expressive qualities, no other part of speech can be compared with adjectives. Since one of the tasks of teaching the Russian language is to teach students to express their thoughts not only correctly, but also accurately, figuratively, there is an urgent need to familiarize students with the figurative properties of adjectives. Unlike the name of a noun, denoting the concept of an object in the aggregate with all its features, the adjective narrows the scope of the concept, makes it concrete and distinct.

In my lesson on the topic "Adjective", I try to explain in detail the expression of the qualitative and relative characteristics of an object, phenomenon and process. I give constructions: what color (shape, size...), what color (shape, size...), what shape (size,

taste, smell, color). For example: These eyes are blue (blue in color, have a blue color). The hat has a cylindrical shape (cylinder shape). A cylindrical hat. The hat is shaped like a cylinder. Next, I give constructions: characteristic of what, has what properties (properties of what to do), what is in the field of what, what from what, what for what, what from where, what with what (what without what), etc. For example: The sense organs have a certain flexibility, which physiologists call adaptation. Man has the ability to adapt to the environment. This is an example from the field of physics. Instrument for measuring.

Since the lesson is held by students of a non-philological university, for example, technical words and phrases, as well as proposals for a specialty, can be cited. Therefore, to describe the property of an object, I recommend that students use the construction possess what (possess the property what to do)? For example: Polymer paper has extraordinary transparency, high strength and chemical resistance. The soil has the ability to retain water and mineral salts necessary for plant nutrition.

It is necessary to explain that constructions with the verb to possess are usually used to describe the positive properties of an object, and to describe the negative properties in scientific speech, the construction with the verb to have is usually used. Further I give a comparison: Compared with an electron lamp, transistors have a number of advantages. - Titanium has one significant drawback - it is its high price.

To characterize the specific, pronounced properties of an object or person, a construction with the verb differ is used:

This guy is distinguished by unusual hardness of character and bright talent.

When explaining the determinative relations, a method of step-by-step passage from one level to another, more complex one, which was mentioned above, will be needed. Therefore, it is necessary to explain that attributive relations can also be expressed in a complex sentence with a definitive clause with an allied word which (-th, -th, -th), that the attributive clause answers the question what? and is located immediately after the word being defined: A commodity is a thing that satisfies human needs.

A union word that agrees with the word being defined in gender and number, and a case form of a union word that depends on its function in the subordinate clause.

Next, to consolidate the grammatical material, you need to perform an exercise. The student must complete the first task at the blackboard so that other students can also join the process - thus, each of them will understand what exactly is required of him. For example: Change these sentences according to the model - *Gold is a yellow metal.* - *Gold is a yellow metal.*

Students can do the rest of the exercises on their own.

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